

Synthesis and antibacterial evaluation of *s*-triazine based chalcones and their derivatives

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Abstract : Various 2-(phenylamino/4'-substituted phenylamino)-4-(phenylamino/4'-substituted phenylamino)-6-[4'-{3''-(4'''-{2'-(5'-ethylpyridin-2'-yl)-ethoxy}-phenyl)-2''-propanon-1''-yl]-phenylamino]-*s*-triazine 6(a-e) were prepared by reaction of different ketones 5(a-e) based on *s*-triazine nucleus and 5-ethylpyridine-2-ethylether of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde. Chalcones 6(a-e) on cyclisation with malanonitrile in the presence of ammonium acetate gave the corresponding cyanopyridines 7(a-e) and on cyclisation with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of alkali gave corresponding isoxazoles 8(a-e). The structures of cyanopyridine derivatives and isoxazole derivatives were confirmed from spectral data. All the synthesized compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against four different strains viz. *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441) (Gram-positive bacteria) and *E. coli* (MTCC-443), *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733) (Gram-negative bacteria) by agar diffusion method.

Keywords : Chalcones, cyanopyridines, isoxazoles, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

s-Triazine based chalcones and their derivatives are important due to their biological activity¹. Cyanopyridine derivatives have attracted considerable attention as they possess antihistaminic², antiproliferative³, antitumor⁴, antihypertensive⁵ and cardiovascular⁶ activities. Isoxazoles have wide range of biological activities such as antiprotozoal⁷, antiviral⁸, antitubercular⁹ and antimicrobial¹⁰. These observations prompted us to synthesise some novel chalcones, cyanopyridines and isoxazoles based on *s*-triazine nucleus.

The classical synthesis of the compounds 6(a-e) involves Claisen-Schmidt condensation of different ketones 5(a-e) based on *s*-triazine nucleus and 5-ethylpyridine-2-ethylether of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde. Chalcones 6(a-e) on cyclisation with malanonitrile in the presence of ammonium acetate and with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of alkali to give the corresponding cyanopyridines 7(a-e) and isoxazoles 8(a-e). The compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity using Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

Results and discussion

Antibacterial activity :

The target molecule were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441) [Gram-positive bacteria] and *E. coli* (MTCC-443), *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733) [Gram-negative bacteria] by using agar diffusion method of Barry¹¹. Known antibiotic Ciprofloxacin was used as standard drug. The screening results indicate that compounds 7(e) and 8(e) were found to be active against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96). Compounds 6(a), 6(d), 7(b), 7(d) and 8(b) were found to be moderately active against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96). Compounds 6(b), 6(e), 7(a), 8(a) and 8(d) were found to be less active against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96), whereas compounds 6(c), 7(c) and 8(c) were found to be inactive against *S. aureus* (MTCC-96). Compounds 6(a), 6(b), 6(d), 6(e), 7(e) and 8(e) were found to be active against *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441). Compounds 6(c), 7(a), 7(b), 7(c), 7(d), 8(a), 8(b) and 8(c) were found to be moderately active against *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441), whereas compound 8(d) was found to be less active against *B. subtilis* (MTCC-441).

Table 1. Molecular formula, melting point and yields of compounds 6(a-e), 7(a-e) and 8(a-e)

Compd.	R	R'	Molecular formula	M.p.	Yield
				(°C)	(%)
6a	H	H	C ₃₉ H ₃₅ N ₇ O ₂	138	70
6b	H	Cl	C ₃₉ H ₃₄ ClN ₇ O ₂	120	72
6c	Cl	Cl	C ₃₉ H ₃₃ Cl ₂ N ₇ O ₂	113	69
6d	F	F	C ₃₉ H ₃₃ F ₂ N ₇ O ₂	146	70
6e	F	Cl	C ₃₉ H ₃₃ ClFN ₇ O ₂	123	71
7a	H	H	C ₄₂ H ₃₆ N ₁₀ O	193	68
7b	H	Cl	C ₄₂ H ₃₅ N ₁₀ ClO	150	66
7c	Cl	Cl	C ₄₂ H ₃₄ N ₁₀ Cl ₂ O	180	59
7d	F	F	C ₄₂ H ₃₄ N ₁₀ F ₂ O	160	63
7e	F	Cl	C ₄₂ H ₃₄ N ₁₀ ClFO	210	65
8a	H	H	C ₃₉ H ₃₅ N ₈ O ₂	203	67
8b	H	Cl	C ₃₉ H ₃₄ ClN ₈ O ₂	183	68
8c	Cl	Cl	C ₃₉ H ₃₃ Cl ₂ N ₈ O ₂	197	60
8d	F	F	C ₃₉ H ₃₃ F ₂ N ₈ O ₂	217	65
8e	F	Cl	C ₃₉ H ₃₃ ClFN ₈ O ₂	215	64

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the compounds 6(a-e), 7(a-e) and 8(a-e)

Compd.	R'	R	Antibacterial activity			
			Diameter of zone of inhibition (in mm)			
			<i>S. aureus</i> (MTCC-96)	<i>B. subtilis</i> (MTCC-441)	<i>E. coli</i> (MTCC-443)	<i>S. paratyphi-B</i> (MTCC-733)
6a	H	H	16	20	16	14
6b	H	Cl	12	19	17	15
6c	Cl	Cl	-	17	16	13
6d	F	F	15	19	17	15
6e	F	Cl	12	21	16	18
7a	H	H	13	16	15	17
7b	H	Cl	16	15	16	15
7c	Cl	Cl	-	14	17	16
7d	F	F	14	17	15	16
7e	F	Cl	18	20	14	17
8a	H	H	11	16	15	15
8b	H	Cl	14	14	16	14
8c	Cl	Cl	-	15	15	15
8d	F	F	12	13	14	14
8e	F	Cl	18	21	18	13
Ciprofloxacin			20	22	24	25
(Standard drug)						

Compounds 6(a), 6(b), 6(c), 6(d), 6(e), 7(a), 7(b), 7(c), 7(d), 7(e), 8(a), 8(b), 8(c) and 8(e) were found to be moderately active against *E. coli* (MTCC-443), where as 7(e) and 8(d) were found to be less active against *E.*

coli (MTCC-443). Compounds 6(b), 6(d), 6(e), 7(a), 7(b), 7(c), 7(d), 7(e), 8(a), 8(b) and 8(c) were found to be moderately active against *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733). Compounds 6(a), 6(c), 8(b), 8(d) and 8(e) were found to

be less active against *S. paratyphi-B* (MTCC-733).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker Avance DPX 400 MHz spectrometer with CDCl₃ and DMSO as solvent and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. TLC was conducted on Silica Gel 60

F-254 (Merck) plates of 0.25 mm thickness.

Preparation of 2-(4'-chlorophenylamino)-4-(4'-fluorophenylamino)-6-[4''-{3''-(4''''-{2''-(5'-ethylpyridin-2'-yl)-ethoxy}-phenyl)-2''-propenon-1''-yl}]-phenylamino}-*s*-triazine (6e) : Compound 5(e) (0.01 mol) was dissolved in DMF (30 mL) and 40% KOH (4 mL) was added to it. Then 5-ethylpyridine-2-ethylether of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was added with constant stirring at

Scheme 1

room temperature. After 24 h, the reaction mixture was poured onto crushed ice and neutralize with HCl. The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol to give **6(e)**. Yield 71 %, m.p. 123 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3056 (=CH str), 1603 (C=C), 827 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 1227 (C-O-C), (1650) C=O, 787 (C-Cl str), 1012 (C-F str), 803 (C-N, *s*-triazine); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 1.24 (3H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 2.48 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 3.16 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 3.44 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 6.92 (1H, d, $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}=\text{}$), 7.2-7.82 (19H, m, 16 Ar-H and 3 NH), 8.06 (1H, d, Ar-CH=).

Preparation of 2-(4'-chlorophenylamino)-4-(4'-fluorophenylamino)-6-[4'-(2''-amino-3''-cyano-4'''-{2'-(5'-ethylpyridin-2'-yl)-ethoxy}-phenyl)-pyridin-6''-yl]-phenylamino]-s-triazine (7e) : Compound **6(e)** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in alcohol (25 mL). Malanonitrile (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate were added to it and refluxed for 8 h. Then the reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto crushed ice. The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol to give **7(e)**. Yield 65 %, m.p. 210 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3050 (=CH str), 1616 (C=C), 829 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 1227 (C-O-C), 786 (C-Cl str), 1012 (C-F str), 2207 (C \equiv N), 807 (C-N, *s*-triazine), 3460 ($-\text{NH}_2$); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO) δ ppm : 1.22 (3H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 2.48 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 3.18 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 3.46 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 6.9 (2H, s, $-\text{NH}_2$), 7.0-7.84 (21H, m, 17 Ar-H and 3 NH).

Preparation of 2-(4'-chlorophenylamino)-4-(4'-fluorophenylamino)-6-[4'-(5''-{4'''-(2'-(5'-ethylpyridin-2'-yl)-ethoxy)-phenyl}-isoxazole-3''-yl)-phenylamino]-s-triazine (8e) : 2-(Phenylamino/4'-substituted phenylamino)-4-(phenylamino/4'-substituted phenylamino)-6-[4'-(3''-(4'''-{2'-(5'-ethylpyridin-2'-yl)-ethoxyphenyl}-2''-propenon-1''-yl)-phenylamino]-s-triazine **6(e)** (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in alcohol (30 mL) were refluxed for 6 h in the presence of 40% KOH (5 mL). The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured onto crushed ice and product obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol to give **8(e)**. Yield 64 %, m.p. 215 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3098 (=CH str), 1598 (C=C), 827 (-CH str, 1,4-substitution), 1229 (C-O-C), 1240 (C-O-N), 780 (C-Cl str), 1013 (C-F str), 1575

(C=N), 809 (C-N, *s*-triazine); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 1.22 (3H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 2.44 (2H, q, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 3.16 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 3.45 (2H, t, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$), 6.7 (1H, s, $-\text{CH}_{\text{isox}}$), 6.94-7.88 (19H, m, 16 Ar-H and 3 NH).

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